

Religiosity as a predictor of Redeemer University Undergraduates' sexual behaviour: Does age, gender and family type have roles to play?

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Abstract

Sexual behaviour associated with young people is becoming alarming, and numerous studies have revealed that religion and religiosity have a significant impact on young people's sexual behaviour. However, little research has been done in Nigeria to examine the moderating role of age, gender and family type on religiosity and sexual behaviour. A descriptive research design was adopted, and purposive sampling techniques were adopted to recruit study respondents from Redeemers' University, Ede, Osun State, via e-questionnaires. One thousand and fifty-two (1052) respondents filled the e-questionnaires. Descriptive, moderation and regression analysis were used in making an inference. The result indicated that 54.1% of the respondents had deep religiosity while 45.9% had superficial religiosity. Respondents with deep religiosity (52.9%) were sexually inactive while those with superficial religiosity were sexually active. The regression analysis revealed that religiosity was able to explain 40% variance in young people's sexual behaviour ($R^2 = 0.40$, $F(1, 1051) = 708.87$, $p < .05$). However, the family type ($\beta = -1.32$ SE = 0.32, $p > .05$) and gender ($\beta = -1.44$ SE = 4.51, $p > .05$) was unable to play a moderating role between religiosity and sexual behaviour relationship. Age ($\beta = -$

6.05 SE = 3.16, $p < .05$) moderates the role of religiosity on young people's sexual behaviour. The study concluded that religiosity is a tool capable of addressing negative consequences of young people's sexual behaviour. The study recommends that university management be cognizant of religiosity as a tool to curb such vices while making social policies concerning young people's sexual behaviour.

Keywords: *Sexual behaviour, Religiosity, Family types, Undergraduates, Religion*

Introduction

A critical time in a person's development is when they are young. Young adulthood is known as "A n je aye Oba" among young people in Yorubaland, which literally translates to "period of fun and enjoyment." These times span from late adolescence to young adulthood, and they portray a time when there is a lot of freedom and fun (drug use and abuse, sexual relationships, and the development of relationships), as well as occasionally less concern for the repercussions (Olaleye, et al., 2020). While some young people are able to engage in protective behaviour, others have had to deal with the repercussions of risky sexual behaviour, despite the focus of some researchers on sexual behaviour among Nigerian youth (Aji, et al, 2013 Omisore, et al, 2022; Lungu, et al, 2022).

Sexual behaviour enacted by most humans differs from one individual to another, and if not well managed, it could lead to anomalies and unbearable social sexual practices (Ekundayo & Babalola, 2020). This practice also exposes individuals to sexually transmitted infections (STI), inclusive HIV, with a prevalence of 17 per cent in the southeastern and 14 per cent in the northern part of Nigeria (Envuladu, et al., 2017). However, in southwest Nigeria, 27.4 percent of youth had an abortion or unintended pregnancy (Owonikoko, et al., 2016). In the southern part of Nigeria, about 32% of cases of unsafe abortion were youth as well (Ikeako, et al., 2014). Studies (such as Pengpid & Peltzer, 2021; Melesse, et al., 2021) have also shown substantial diversity in sexual behaviour by region resulting in late marriage and an increase in premarital sexual behaviour among youths; and higher in men than in women (Melesse, et al., 2021).

Deductively, people may think that these challenges or freedom of youth in schools could be avoided through careful selection of universities. Thus, faith-based universities appeared to be the right choice since these kinds of universities give sanctions against sexual activity in South western

Nigeria. Despite, several underlying mechanisms that initiate sexual maturation process to sociocultural forces and differences. The above form the rationale for this study to examine the prevailing levels of young peoples' sexual behaviour in faith-based universities in Osun State Nigeria

Present study rationale

The formation of one's morality and good judgment, which impact the choices that shape one's life, is significantly influenced by religious beliefs and practices (Agbetunde, et al., 2020). Through the internalization of religious morality, religion enhances the development of moral consciousness. Alongside faith-based institution capabilities to foster analytical reasoning, which seeks information and comprehension of the science and education that describes our reality and examines and queries how this knowledge should or should be employed in the context of faith or religion. Arguably this indicates that religion should be able to curb excessive sexual behaviours considering its injunctions and practices. Yet, studies (Shimie, et al., 2022; Ayalew Tegegne, 2022; Albright & Allen, 2018) indicated a high prevalence of sexual transmitted disease and unwanted pregnancy among young people despite their religious inclinations.

Religion is said to have social control functions for individuals within a society, and it appears that religious adolescents are less likely than their fewer religious peers to engage in delinquent activities and risky sexual behaviour (Obasola, 2013, Pope, Price & Lillard, 2014, Somefun, 2019). Despite the fact that several studies have established a link between religiosity and high or risky sexual behaviour (such as Agbetunde, et al 2020; Erafti, 2019), there is still a need to understand the impact of family ties and/or family type on such a link. This is practical because humans are socialised first in their families. There is also a connection between family type and religiosity as religion is one way that families socialise their children. Religion is frequently used by parents to convey important messages about values and to establish behavioural expectations. Religion also encourages active sexual behaviour through rites and limitations that are typically enforced by custodians. Religion, for example, encourages both single and multiple sex partners, which serve as the foundation for the various family types (monogamy and polygamy) that exist in Nigeria (Olaniyan, 2016).

Due to the increasing prevalence of sexual behaviour as identified above, this study seeks to examine the moderating role of parent's marital style or family type (monogamy and polygamy), age (adolescence and young

adulthood) and gender (male and female) between religiosity and young peoples' sexual behaviour.

Method

Respondents

Respondents of this study were selected via purposive sampling techniques. The respondents were undergraduates' students from Redeem University Ede (n=1052) in Osun State, Nigeria. The age of the respondents was within 18 to 30 years old ($M=22.67$, $SD=3.93$). Majority of the respondents were male (n=651, 82.4%), single (n=1030, 97.9%), monogamy (n=727, 69.1%), polygamy (n=325, 30.9%), deep religiosity (n=569, 54.1%), superficial religiosity (n=483, 45.9%).

Measures

Personal Information Questionnaire: This research instrument was used to gather information on family type background, age, marital status, religion, institutions and gender. Three of these items (marital status, religion, gender) on the questionnaire were closed-ended while others were open-ended.

Religious Orientation Test: This scale was designed and developed by Idehen, (2001) to measure religious orientation. The scale consists of 6-items and two types of religious orientation were also identified. These are: deep and superficial religious orientation. Respondents are to rate themselves on a 5-point Likert scale. Respondents' responses are scored from most positive to the most negative. More so, low scores indicate a deep religious orientation while high scores indicate a superficial religious orientation. Idehen, (2001) used the religious orientation test on a sample of 160 and reported alpha values between 0.76 and 0.80 along with 0.80 and 0.75 internal consistency Cronbach alpha and test re-test reliability correlation respectively. Effort was further made to ascertain this through conducting a validation exercise. A concurrent validity was carried out using the Gorsuch and Venables (1983) religious orientation scale (ROS) which was a modification of Allport (1960) religious orientation scale. The report of the validation exercise indicated that there is a positive correlation ($r(48) = .62$) between the scales (ROT VS ROS). Likewise, the reliability analysis indicated 0.70 Cronbach Alpha, hence the scale measures what its puppet to measure and fit to be used in the present study.

Sexual Behavioural Scale: The items in this section were adapted from Oyedeji (2010). The SBS consist of 24 items that elicit responses to patterns

of sexual activity in the last four weeks. The scale showed a series of sexual activities likely to be engaged in by the respondents. The item scores range from Not at all (0), through once (1), to twice (2), to thrice (3), and more (4). The scale categorizes sexual behaviour into two which are penetrative and non-penetrative with each of these categorizations being further divided into sexually inactive and active within the last four weeks. Penetrative sexual behaviour refers to sexual activity during which the genital is inserted into the mouth, rectus, or vaginal of a partner. Non-penetrative sexual behaviour refers to the exhibition or engagement of sexual acts such as kiss, hug, talk about sex, intimate eye contact, caressing each other's genitals among others which can be performed with or without another person. Sexually inactive, on the other hand, refers to the disengage in sexual activities within the last four weeks. In other words, individual with zero frequency of sexual acts falls under this category (sexually inactive) while individual with frequency of sexual activities within 1-4times within the last four weeks fall within the category of sexually active. The scale was subjected to concurrent validation with the Oyedeji (2010) version using Pearson moment correlation ($r(48) = .83$). The result obtained indicated positive correlation and as such by implication the adapted version of Sexual behaviour Scale measured what it also set out to measure and half-fit to be used in the main study. Likewise, the 24-items of the Sexual behaviour scale were subjected to reliability analysis. The scale yielded a reliability of 0.7.

Procedure

Redeemers University in Osun State, Nigeria was specifically chosen as the source of respondents. The goal was to investigate the relationship between young people's sexual behaviour and religiosity in a religious context. The sampling strategy used was purposive sampling. Three faculties are purposefully chosen for the study. (Faculty of Basic Medical Science, Faculty of Natural Science, Faculty of Social Science) out of nine faculties in Redeemer's University. This decision was made with the intention of ensuring the collection of high-quality data and having a sufficient number of proportionate study population representatives. In addition, three departments from the aforementioned faculties were specifically chosen for the study's sample of respondents. Thus, the departments of nursing, public health, medicine (Faculty of Basic Medical Science), mass communication, economic, behavioural sciences (Faculty of Social Sciences), Mathematics, chemical science, and biological sciences

(Faculty of Natural sciences) were selected from Redeemers’ University, Ede.

In an attempt to ensure quality and transparent data collection, an online questionnaire was adopted. A script was designed using excel to launch the e-questionnaire via Kobotool box. Kobotool box was used because it controls for missing values and permits transparency and could also be used without an active data plan provided by the server company. Links of the questionnaire generated were circulated among students via WhatsApp groups to disseminate information. Thus, a total of one thousand and fifty-three respondents filled the form within four weeks (October-November, 2022).

Statistical analysis

Preliminary data analysis was carried out though data cleaning, outliers, and out-of-range scores were conducted before the main analysis. The variables' normality, linearity, and homoscedasticity, as well as their multicollinearity, were all checked. The goal here was to look at the distributions of individual variables, identify outliers, define the data's outstanding features, ensure conventional statistical assumptions were met and prepare the data for further analysis. Data cleaning was checked at the point of data collection through the use of Kobotool which ensured that missing data or incomplete questionnaires were not submitted while Z-scores and Mahalanobis distance were employed to screen for univariate and multivariate outliers, respectively. There were no univariate outlier cases found in this study with a Z-score of greater than 3.29 or less than -3.39. In addition, no major multivariate outliers were found in the present investigation for any of the predictor variables that surpassed the criteria value of p.001. The rationale for checking for outliers is to avoid observations that deviate remarkably from the data observation. This is necessary to avoid corruption of data sets and findings.

Table 1: Descriptive statistics and normality analysis of the study variables

	N	Mini mum	Maxi mum	Mea n	S td. Deviatio n	Skew ness	Kurto sis
Family Type	1052	1.00	2.00	1.30	0.46	0.83	-1.31

Sexual Behaviour	105 2	0.00	92.00	29.28	26.13	0.	-0.82
						:	
						:	
Religiosity	105 2	6.00	30.00	22.15	6.68	-0.8	-0.71

The skewness and kurtosis of the distribution were also analyzed to see if the data met the univariate normality assumption. The skewness values for the variables varied between -0.53 and -0.83, whereas the kurtosis values varied between -0.82 and -1.31. Thus, these values are within the permitted range of +2 and -2 as defined by Mowbray, et al., (2019). Thus, indicating that the set of data met the basic univariate normality assumption. The Multicollinearity test for the research variables was provided in Table 2. The variance inflation factor (VIF) and tolerance levels were used to test the multicollinearity assumption as illustrated below:

Table 2: Multicollinearity test among the predictor variables

Independent variables	Collinearity Statistics	
	Tolerance value	VIF
Family Type	0.99	1.00
Religiosity	0.99	1.00

Dependent Variable: Sexual Behaviour

Table 2 shows that tolerance values for the research variables ranged from 0.99 to 0.99, which is within the tolerance threshold of larger than 0.1 (tolerance value), while variance inflation factor (VIF) values are one, which is within the fewer than ten range (Kim, 2019). As a result, the results show no multicollinearity in this investigation.

Lastly, Inferential statistics were used to test assumptions to reach a decisive conclusion. To this end, regression analysis and moderation

analysis were used to ascertain the study argument that religiosity predicts young people's behaviour. Likewise, family type does also have a moderation role in this relationship. The rationale was to see how the independent variables could predict (independently and jointly) the dependent variable. Likewise, estimating the relationship between two quantitative variables with how strongly the independent variable and dependent variable could be moderated by family type.

Results

The descriptive analysis indicated that 54.1% of the respondents had deep religiosity as against 45.9% with superficial religiosity. The goal is to describe young people's sexual behaviour in relation to their religiosity. Demonstratively:

Figure 1: Descriptive Framework

The above indicates the descriptive analysis was observed from angles of religiosity dimension. Table 3 summary religiosity and young peoples' Sexual Behaviour (SB).

Table 3: Descriptive Analysis of Religiosity and Young peoples' Sexual Behaviour

Religiosity Level	SB Categories	SB levels	N/ %	Frequency	Percent %
Deep Religiosity	Penetrative	Sexually active	569, 54.1%	268	47.1
		Sexually inactive		301	52.9
	Non penetrative	Sexually active		569	100
		Sexually inactive		--	--
Superficial Religiosity	Penetrative	Sexually active	454	94.0	
		Sexually inactive	29	6.0	

	Non penetrative	Sexually active	483, 45.9%	458	94.8
		Sexually inactive		25	5.2

Penetrative sexual behaviour refers to sexual activities such as oral, anal, virginal sex, transactional sex, unprotected sex and sex with someone other than his/her partner. In contrast, non-penetrative sex refers to sexual behaviours such as a hug, kissing, fondling, caressing each other's genitals, watching pornography, masturbation and fantasizing. However, sexually inactive refers to an individual who did not look at all exhibit such behaviour in the last four weeks, while sexually active refers to an individual who had exhibited such behaviour either one to four times within the last four weeks. Table 3 shows that 52.9% of the respondents are not sexually active concerning penetrative sexual behaviours, in contrast to 47.1% who are. All the respondents with deep religiosity practice non-penetrative sexual behaviour. Most respondents with superficial religiosity (94% and 94.8%) engage in penetrative and non-penetrative sexual behaviour.

For further investigation on how religiosity predicts young peoples' sexual behaviour, the Table 4 indicated the summary of the regression analysis:

Table 4: Linear Regression Summary Table Showing Predictive Role of Young peoples' Sexual Behaviour

<i>Variable</i>	<i>B</i>	<i>SE</i>	β	<i>t</i>	<i>P</i>
(Constant)	84.28	2.16		39.06	.000
Religiosity	-2.48	0.09	-0.64	-26.63	0.00

($R^2 = 0.40$, $F(1, 1051) = 708.87$, $p < .05$)

Table 4 indicated that religiosity significantly predicted undergraduate behaviour ($R^2 = 0.40$, $F(1, 1051) = 708.87$, $p < .05$). The result showed that religiosity explained 40-percent variance in young peoples' sexual behaviour though the remaining 60-percent could be due to other factors

not accounted for in the present study. The table also indicated that the regression model was a good fit.

Moderation analysis was also conducted to examine the moderating role of family type in the relationship between religiosity and sexual behaviour. Process Macro was used in achieving these. The table below shows the summary of the analysis:

Table 5: Moderation effect of family type in the association between religiosity and sexual behaviour

Model	B	SE	t	95% CI	P
LLCI (ULCI)					
Constant	3.75**	0.42	10.61	56.18 (81.44)	0.00
Religiosity	-0.73**	0.12	-8.28	-40.63(-25.06)	0.00
Family type	-1.32	0.32	1.01	-4.49(13.94)	0.32
Religiosity**fa mily type → Sexual behaviour	0.41	0.08	0.84	3.21(8.04)	0.40
	R ²	0.34			
	F(df)	F(1, 1051)			
		=0.71			

Results as shown in table 5 revealed that there is a statistically significant direct effect of religiosity on young people's sexual behaviour ($\beta = -0.73$ SE = 0.12, $p < .05$). Although, family type does not have a direct relationship with young people's sexual behaviour ($\beta = -1.32$ SE = 0.32, $p > .05$). Thus,

family type was unable to intervene between the predictive role of religiosity on sexual behaviour.

More so, the study also observes the moderation effect of age in the relationship between religiosity and young people's sexual behaviour. Age was categorised based on age gap 15-24 (adolescence) and 25-30 (young adult). The table below provides a summary of the moderation analysis using process macro.

Table 6: Moderation effect of Age in the association between religiosity and sexual behaviour

Model	β	SE	t	95% CI	P
				LLCI (ULCI)	
Constant	59.94**	6.96	8.60	46.27 (73.60)	0.00
Religiosity	-22.29**	4.22	-5.27	-30.59(-13.99)	0.00
Age	12.43**	5.48	2.26	1.67(23.18)	0.02
Religiosity**Age* *Sexual behaviour	-6.05	3.16	-1.91	-12.27(0.15)	0.05
	R ²	0.32			
	F(df)	F(3, 1048) =162.31			

The result above indicated that age was able to moderate how religiosity predicts young people sexual behaviour. Thus, age (developmental phases) intervenes in the predictive role of religiosity on young people's sexual behaviour ($\beta = -6.05$ SE = 3.16, $p < .05$) and had a direct relationship with young peoples' sexual behaviour ($\beta = 12.43$ SE = 5.48, $p < .05$). Further moderation analysis was also carried out on the role of gender in the

relationship between religiosity and sexual behaviour. The Table 7 below indicated a summary of the analysis.

Table 7: Moderation effect of Gender in the association between religiosity and sexual behaviour

Model	β	SE	t	95% CI	P
				LLCI (ULCI)	
Constant	72.57**	6.49	11.18	59.84 (85.31) 0.00	
Religiosity	-28.75**	4.03	-7.13	-36.67(-20.84) 0.00	
Gender	1.44	4.51	0.32	-7.40(10.29) 0.74	
Religiosity**Gender**Sexual behaviour	-0.45	2.76	-0.16	-5.88(4.96) 0.86	
	R ²	0.31			
	F(df)	F(3, 1048) =159.49			

Source: Author Field-data 2022

Table 7 indicated that gender was unable to moderate the predictive role of religiosity in young peoples’ sexual behaviour in Redeemers’ University Ede, Osun State, Nigeria. Gender does not have a moderating predictive role between religiosity and young peoples’ sexual behaviour ($\beta = 1.44$ SE = 4.51, $p > .05$) despite religiosity having a direct relationship with sexual behaviour ($\beta = -28.75$ SE = -7.13, $p < .05$).

Discussion and conclusion

The study claimed that religiosity could predict young people's sexual behaviour though family type was unable to influence how religiosity predicted sexual behaviour in young people. Respondents with deep religiosity were, on average, less sexually active than those with superficial religiosity, who tended to be more sexually active (in relation to penetrative sexual behavioural pattern). As a result, young people who are sexually active are very prevalent, especially among respondents who engage in superficial religiosity. This finding supports those of Mavhandu-Mudzusi and Tesfay-Asgedom (2016) and Olaleye et al. (2020), who discovered that undergraduate students were more likely to be sexually active even though the study did not take the respondents' religious affiliation into consideration. Studies have shown that religion helps to reduce the sexual behaviour that is becoming more common among young people. using number line review analysis to look at two continuums of phenomena. According to the aforementioned premises, some factors may affect sexual behaviour in a way that makes it more normal, while other factors may make it more abnormal (Walton et al., 2016). (Efrati, 2018; Efrati & Gola, 2018). The analysis of the data showed a negative correlation between sexual behaviour and religiosity. This suggests that an improvement in religiosity will result in an improvement in sexual behaviour. The results of the current study suggested that religiosity might affect sexual behaviour in a normalising way. Hence, there is a need to capitalise on and revive young people's religiosity levels. It was believed that the population under investigation (young people) was most susceptible to sexually transmitted infections and other harmful effects of sexual behaviour (Mavhandu-Mudzusi, and Tesfay-Asgedom, 2016; Ekundayo & Babalola, 2020; Obiyan, et al., 2021; Maina, et al., 2021). They become more susceptible to sexually transmitted diseases as a result of their sexual exploration and initiation, as well as any subsequent engagement in unsafe sex (excessive sexual behaviour). Thus, religion is essential in minimising the aforementioned social vices in order to safeguard them and prevent them from occurring. Furthermore, the relationship between religiosity and sexual behaviour was moderated by age (adolescence and early adulthood. Despite this, respondents with high religiosity are more likely than those with superficial religiosity to engage in safe sexual behaviour (both penetrative and non-penetrative). This might imply that an undergraduate becomes more sexually active as they get older. This indicates that early-adult undergraduates exhibit more penetrative sexual behaviour than adolescents. According to the findings

of this study, family type was unable to intervene in the relationship between religiosity and sexual behaviour. This might be because religion and religiosity have a strong influence on Nigerian than family type. A religious person is more likely to abstain from sexual activity or have safe sexual activities than a person from either a monogamous family type or polygamous family type. In a similar view, Ekundayo and Babalola, (2020) found that age, family type and peer pressure had an intervening impact on the influence of impulsivity on sexual risk behaviour of university undergraduates in Nigeria. Thus, their findings indicated that family type was able to moderate the relationship between impulsivity and sexual risk behaviour. These discrepancies may result from the religious university's study area being different from Ekundayo and Babalola's (2020).

The study concluded that there are high levels of sexual activeness among young people with superficial religiosity as opposed to young people with deep religiosity in religiously based settings. Religion is a tool for mitigating the negative consequences of young people's sexual behaviour. Family type, on the other hand, was unable to moderate the relationship between religiosity and sexual behaviour.

Recommendation

According to the study's findings, undergraduate students' environments should be modified to limit the negative consequences of sexual behaviour through policy formation and development that recognizes religiosity as a tool for sexual behavioural modification. Furthermore, university administration must educate students about healthy decisions and the consequences of negative sexual behaviour. Sexual orientation programmes offered by faith-based university administration may also aid in combating this vice. Similarly, the study suggests that future research can employ other research strategies, such as qualitative, to provide a more in-depth reflection of the research issue in the real world. Other studies can also benefit from mixed methodology.

Ethical approval

This study was approved by the Department of Psychology, Obafemi Awolowo University and postgraduate committees for ethical committees.

Declaration of conflicting of interest

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Author contribution

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